

Studies on Ni-Clay Membrane

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The fixed ion concentration in the membrane phase gives the quantitative information regarding biionic potential across a membrane and the diffusion potential contributes very little to overall membrane potential.

In a previous communication¹ it was suggested that nature of ion-saturation of clay can influence the electrical potential developed across a clay membrane separating two aqueous solutions of 1 : 1 electrolyte at different concentrations. It was also shown that the electrical potential across a membrane separating electrolytic solutions of a particular electrolyte depends on $\omega\bar{x}$ i.e., fixed ion concentration² in the membrane phase and $\omega\bar{x}$ changes for the same membrane depending on the nature of electrolyte. This gives us an opportunity to undertake extensive experimental work on a particular clay membrane and results of which are reported in this paper.

Theoretical : According to the T.M.S. theory³, the membrane potential across a membrane is :

$$E_M = \text{Diffusion potential} + \text{two Donnan}$$

(Membrane potential) potentials at two interfaces.

If we consider Diffusion potential = 0

$$E_M = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{r_2}{r_1} \quad (\text{for 1 : 1 electrolyte})$$

where r = Donnan distribution ratio at the particular interface denoted by the subscript

$$r = \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\omega\bar{x}}{2a}\right)^2} - \left(\frac{\omega\bar{x}}{2a}\right)$$

where $\omega\bar{x}$ = fixed-ion concentration in the membrane phase concentration of ionizable groups expressed in Normality/Kg H₂O.

a = activity of ext. electrolyte solution with which the membrane is in contact.

1. M. Adhikari and D. Ghosh. 1970, **47**, 384 *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*
2. M. Adhikari and D. Ghosh, Communicated to *Indian J. Chem.*
3. I. Altug and M. L. Hair, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1968, **72**, 599.

Thus for the following cell arrangement

there will not develop any electrical potential across the membrane. When the cell arrangement is as given below

the e.m.f. developed can be used to evaluate $\omega\bar{x}$ in the membrane phase by computation.

When the membrane separates two aq. solns. of two unlike 1:1 electrolyte at same activity as below :

there is generation of an electrical potential which is generally known as Bi-ionic potential. With implicit assumption that diffusion potential contributes nothing towards cell potential when a membrane cell is set up, we can calculate $\omega\bar{x}$ from a number of measurements when membrane separates solutions at different activities of the same electrolyte. It is found that with nature of electrolyte $\omega\bar{x}$ varies. Thus let us assume that $\omega\bar{x} = (\omega\bar{x})_{MA}$ when one side of membrane is in contact with MA (1:1) and it is $(\omega\bar{x})_{M'A}$ when other side of membrane is in contact with electrolyte $M'A$ as shown below

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} E_M = E_{B.I.P.} &= \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\omega\bar{x}_{MA}}{2a_1}\right)^2} - \left(\frac{\omega\bar{x}_{MA}}{2a_1}\right)}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\omega\bar{x}_{M'A}}{2a_1}\right)^2} - \left(\frac{\omega\bar{x}_{M'A}}{2a_1}\right)} \\ &= \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{r_2}{r'_1} \end{aligned}$$

But according to previous workers⁴ for above cell

$$E_{B-I.P.} = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{\bar{U}_{M^+}}{\bar{U}_{M'^+}}$$

where \bar{U} terms refer to mobility of the ion in the membrane phase.

Comparing above two equations we can write

$$\frac{r'_2}{r'_1} = \frac{\bar{U}_{M^+}}{\bar{U}_{M'^+}}$$

EXPERIMENTAL

H-Clay from Chinsurah (0-6") (mostly montmorillonite clay) soil was prepared by usual method of sedimentation, dispersion, followed by dialysis. H-clay was then exchanged with NiSO_4 to produce Ni-H clay (with 70% exchangeable Ni^{2+}) which was then converted to thin films by evaporation of 3% of this clay suspension and heated in muffle furnace at $550 \pm 10^\circ$ for 48 hrs. The dried clay film after exchanging with H^+ , was analysed for Ni content in the matrix and was found to contain about 10% Ni^{2+} .

Fired clay plates were then sealed to pyrex tubings by means of an adhesive (polystyrene dissolved in toluene)

E.M.F.'s of membrane cell

were determined by means of two tiny calomel electrodes serving as reference electrodes having asymmetry less than ± 0.2 mv.

Readings were recorded by means of a Leeds Northrup K_2 type potentiometer—Leeds Northrup Galvanometer assembly at room temperature and in each case temperature was recorded.

All chemicals used were A.R. Grade.

4. N. Lakshminarayanaiah, *Chem. Rev.* (1965). Transport processes in artificial membrane, p. 507.
5. A. N. Basu and S. K. Mukherjee, *J. Indian Soc. Soil. Sci.* 1966, **14**, 92.

RESULTS

TABLE I

Readings with aq. soln. of KCl

Temp. in °C	Inside soln. in normality	Outside soln. in normality	E.M.F. in mv	Theo. E.M.F. in mV on the basis of $\omega\bar{x} = 0.07(N)$ at 30°
28.5	(+) .003	(-) .006	17.85	17.77
27	(+) .006	(-) .012	16.75	16.74
29	(+) .012	(-) .024	15.40	15.34

Readings with aq. soln. of NaCl

Temp. in °C	Inside soln. in normality	Outside soln. in normality	E.M.F. in mv	Theo. E.M.F. in mV on the basis of $\omega\bar{x} = 0.095(N)$ at 30°
27	(+) .003	(-) .006	17.0	17.20
25	(+) .006	(-) .012	17.1	16.94
27	(+) .012	(-) .024	16.0	16.01
28	(+) .024	(-) .048	14.6	14.47

Readings with aq. solns. of HCl

Temp. in °C	Inside soln. in normality	Outside soln. in normality	E.M.F. in mv	Theo. E.M.F. in mV
26	(+) .003	(-) .006	8.8	not calculated
29	(+) .006	(-) .012	9.55	-do-

TABLE II

Temp. in °C	Inside soln. in normality	Outside soln. in normality	Obs. E.M.F. in mV	Theo. E.M.F. in mV $E = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{r_{MA}}{r_{M'A}}$ at 30°
28	(-) .003 KCl	(+) .003 NaCl	7.5	7.508
28	(-) .003 HCl	(+) .003 KCl	25.0	—
28	(-) .006 HCl	(+) .003 KCl	33.45	—
28	(-) .012 HCl	(+) .003 KCl	42.5	—

DISCUSSION

Results of our experiments have revealed that $\omega\bar{x}$ in the membrane phase varies with nature of cation of electrolyte with which the membrane is in contact. With C_S form clay membrane $\omega\bar{x}$ was observed to be $0.055(N)^2$ and was independent of temperature of pre-treatment whereas when same clay was converted into Ni-form, $\omega\bar{x}$ became $0.07(N)$, when KCl was used as external electrolyte solution. But with NaCl as ext. electrolyte soln. $\omega\bar{x}$

became 0.095 (N). Further Bi-ionic potential can be quantitatively predicted provided $\omega\bar{x}$ values are known when membrane is in contact with two different electrolytes (see Table II). $\omega\bar{x}$ value in the membrane phase becomes very small when membrane is in contact with aq. soln. of HCl. This is quite expected since Ni-clay membrane exchanged with HCl before using to determine ionic activity of H^+ in aq. HCl solns. behaves as a weak acid whose ionization correspondingly $\omega\bar{x}$ becomes very small in presence of a strong electrolyte like HCl, due to common ion effect. Considering the value of $\omega\bar{x}$, when membrane is in contact with aq. soln. of HCl as x (N), when according to the deduction of $E_{B.I.P.}$ for a membrane separating aq. HCl and KCl solns.

$$E_{B.I.P.} = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{x}{2a}\right)^2} - \left(\frac{x}{2a}\right)}{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{.07}{2a}\right)^2} - \left(\frac{.07}{2a}\right)}$$

$$= \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{r_2}{r_1} \quad \text{considering activities of both HCl and and KCl are same.}$$

With different HCl activities under constant activity of KCl.

$$E_{B.I.P.} = \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{r_3}{r_1}$$

Hence, the difference between two such $B.I.P.$ values would be the potential observed when only HCl solutions separate the membrane. This is found to be the fact as shown in Table III.

TABLE III

E.M.F. with aq. solns. of HCl	E.M.F. difference when membrane is separated by .003(N) KCl but unlike concns. of HCl.
.003(N)/.006(N) = 8.8 mV.	.003(N)HCl/.006(N)HCl = 33.45 - 25.0 = 8.45 mV at 28°.
.006(N)/.012(N) = 9.55 mV at 29°	.006(N)HCl/.012(N)HCl = 42.5 - 33.45 = 9.05 mV at 28°.

Thus it is found from these results, that in case of clay membranes diffusion potential contributes very little to overall membrane potential and only $\omega\bar{x}$ value can give quantitative information regarding $B.I.P.$ across a membrane.